

Please Cite as:

Khadivar, A., Abbas, F. (2013). Method for Measuring Information Technology Program Risk by Fuzzy Approach. IT Management Studies, 1(3), 47-69.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3352621

Method for Measuring Information Technology Program Risk by Fuzzy Approach

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Abstract

Information technology program is composed of several related projects which managing them with each other and program management integrated these efforts but it does not manage project independent. The main factor that causes failing in these information technology programs is less attention to the risk management topics. Information technology program risk management forms based on aware of methods and tools used for assessing and reducing risk and presents solutions to protect organizations against common problems in information technology programs and increase success probabilities. In these programs, risks are not independent, so we should measure these dependencies and we consider this issue in this survey. First we introduce a method for measuring risks by considering their dependencies, then present a methodology for measuring information technology program risks by fuzzy method and also we offered a method for risk classification. Using this method at Asikoda program shows effectiveness of proposed methods

Keywords

Information technology program risk management; risk measuring; risk dependencies; Design Structure Matrix; Fuzzy approach; Asikoda program.